

WP 2650 – Project Description

Data Access

Data availability

- Selection of **Terrascope platform**, Jupyter notebooks on the Terrascope server to access Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3 data within a defined spatial and temporal window.
- **Sentinel-2**: Bio-geophysical products available at 10m resolution are FAPAR, LAI, NDVI from January 2020 to the present moment:
 - 10 m resolution FAPAR V2 from January 2020
 - 10 m resolution LAI V2 from January 2020
 - 10 m resolution NDVI V2 from January 2020
- **Sentinel-3/CGLS**: Sentinel-3 based bio-geophysical products are currently available on the platform as used for generating the Copernicus Global Land (CGLS) product from July 2020. Products before that time are generated with input data from Proba-V. Currently available on Terrascope using the VITO openEO API are:
 - 1 km resolution FAPAR V2 until July 2020 (10-daily).
 - 300 m resolution FAPAR V2 until July 2020 (10-daily).
 - 1 km resolution LAI V2 until July 2020 (10-daily).
 - 300 m resolution LAI V1 until present (10-daily).
- Data accessed as time series over station with defined footprint. Gives the median value over the defined area with a standard deviation value for each time point.
- **ICOS data**: Measurement availability depends on each station. Access to archive data for each station is possible through a combination of ICOS API and custom requests.
 - Photosynthetic Photon Flux Density (PPFD) measurements used for calculating FAPAR value available in the *'meteo'* files (inclusion of archive data has been tested but does not add any information), based on publication *Carrara et al. 2018*. Below canopy measurements are available for a limited number of stations.
 - For radiation measurements, the height of the instrument and the exact location can be extracted from the instrument data in the archive.
 - Uncertainty is estimated in *Carrara et al. 2018*.
 - LAI measurements are available as ancillary data in the archive, uncertainty is given by the standard deviation from all measurements across the plot.
 - Further information has been provided directly by the ICOS Ecosystem Thematic center. This includes the .kmz file of target areas and plot specific measurements of LAI at some sites (*Deliverables\S24ICOS_terrascope\GAI_ICOS.csv*).

Spatial and temporal representativeness

Temporal match-up and representativeness

- **Radiation measurements** are continuous, aggregated as half-hourly measurements for the whole plot from all instruments available.
 - **Sentinel-2**: Match-up with the closest measurement at overpass time.
 - **Sentinel-3/CGLS**: Aggregation of 10-day period measurements at daily overpass time.
- **LAI measurements** are conducted a few times a year/irregularly depending on the station. Daily match-ups with Sentinel data are seldom available.
 - Interpolation of satellite data (continuous and regular data available).

- Daily-match up of LAI measurements with interpolated satellite data for Sentinel-2 and Sentinel-3/CGLS with a flag for interpolation.

Spatial match-up and representativeness

- Assessment of spatial representativeness based on *Román et al. 2009*.
 - Trying to estimate how big an area around the station (i.e. how many pixels) can be validated with the in-situ measurements based on semi-variograms of Sentinel-2.
- No information about position of LAI measurements, but footprint of radiation measurements can be estimated with knowledge of the FOV and the tower height.

Tool

User chooses station, data source and data product. Satellite measurements are then matched-up with the available in-situ data (+/- one month) and displayed as

- a line plot covering the whole time series, including measurement uncertainties (standard deviation for satellite retrievals, estimated uncertainty for radiation measurements (propagated for all measurements used to calculate ground FAPAR), standard deviation for ground LAI),
- a scatter plot, plotting in-situ vs satellite measurements with RMSE, R^2 , etc.,
- a table showing in-situ and satellite measurements for each day.